

REPORT ON VISUAL MEDIA LITERACY IN EUROPE

CLIP critical
visual
media
literacy and
empowerment

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About CLIP

CLIP “Critical visual media literacy and empowerment” aims to strengthen digital capabilities of the Higher Education (HE) sector, and increase critical visual literacy competences, that is a fundamental component of the way European students and citizens are getting informed in the digital era.

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CLIP is implemented by:

- UNIMED - Mediterranean Universities Union
- IULM University
- Hellenic Open University
- ALL DIGITAL

More information on the Project can be found at: <https://clipproject.eu/>

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Executive Summary

With the widespread dominance of visual media across various platforms, ranging from social media to news outlets and entertainment industries, the way knowledge is acquired and disseminated has undergone a significant transformation.

This report investigates the deep impact of images on contemporary culture and how they redefine the concept of education. Especially with the advent of digital technologies, images are increasingly becoming an integral part of the (cultural) environment that surrounds us transforming the way knowledge is acquired and shared. Universities play a crucial role in navigating and shaping this profound cultural transition.

That is why a key focus of CLIP's efforts lies in promoting critical visual literacy into academic curricula, recognizing its fundamental role in shaping the information consumption habits of European students in the digital age. To achieve this goal, the CLIP project developed a micro-learning course on critical visual literacy.

To properly understand the importance of visual literacy, the report begins by exploring the origin of the term "visual culture," which dates to the 1920s. The report proceeds to explore the emergence in the 1990s of the two main fields of visual studies – the German and the Anglo-American traditions.

After this brief introduction, the report gets into the heart of the project, exploring exemplary practices in the field of visual communication and visual literacy in Europe. The partners not only considered European projects but also took into consideration the guidelines provided by the American Professional Association of College & Research Libraries to define the competencies that visually literate students should acquire during their higher education.

Finally, the partners conducted in-depth conversations with visual scholars and practitioners. These experts helped to understand the importance of improving visual literacy skills in both academic education and daily life.

To design the micro-learning course, the partners decided on a structure consisting of an introduction and four modules. These modules cover all the essential aspects related to images, drawing from valuable insights gathered through interviews and extensive research on best practices. This double approach ensures the inclusion of significant subjects, equipping students with a profound comprehension of the role of visuals and the skills to critically interact with images.

In conclusion, after completing the micro-learning course we expect that students will possess the competencies of a visually literate individual.

Περίληψη

Με την ευρεία επικράτηση των οπτικών μέσων σε διάφορες πλατφόρμες, από τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης έως τα ειδησεογραφικά πρακτορεία και τις βιομηχανίες ψυχαγωγίας, ο τρόπος απόκτησης και διάδοσης της γνώσης έχει υποστεί σημαντικό μετασχηματισμό.

Η παρούσα έκθεση διερευνά τον βαθύ αντίκτυπο των εικόνων στον σύγχρονο πολιτισμό και τον τρόπο με τον οποίο επαναπροσδιορίζουν την έννοια της εκπαίδευσης. Ειδικά με την έλευση των ψηφιακών τεχνολογιών, οι εικόνες γίνονται όλο και περισσότερο αναπόσπαστο μέρος του (πολιτιστικού) περιβάλλοντος που μας περικλείει μεταβάλλοντας τον τρόπο με τον οποίο η γνώση αποκτάται και διαδίδεται. Τα Πανεπιστήμια διαδραματίζουν κρίσιμο ρόλο στην καθοδήγηση και τη διαμόρφωση αυτής της βαθιάς πολιτισμικής μετάβασης.

Αυτός είναι ο λόγος για τον οποίο μια βασική προτεραιότητα του έργου CLIP συνίσταται στην προώθηση του κριτικού οπτικού εγγραμματισμού στα ακαδημαϊκά Προγράμματα Σπουδών, αναγνωρίζοντας το θεμελιώδη ρόλο του στη διαμόρφωση των συνηθειών «κατανάλωσης» πληροφοριών των Ευρωπαίων φοιτητριών/ φοιτητών στη σημερινή ψηφιακή εποχή. Για την επίτευξη αυτού του στόχου, στο πλαίσιο του CLIP αναπτύχθηκε ένα Μάθημα μικρομάθησης στη θεματική του κριτικού οπτικού γραμματισμού.

Για να κατανοήσουμε σωστά τη σημασία του «οπτικού (εγ)γραμματισμού», η έκθεση ξεκινά με τη διερεύνηση της προέλευσης του όρου "οπτική κουλτούρα", ο οποίος χρονολογείται από τη δεκαετία του 1920. Εν συνεχεία, προχωρά με τη διερεύνηση της εμφάνισης, στη δεκαετία του 1990, των δύο κύριων πεδίων των οπτικών σπουδών: της Γερμανικής και της Αγγλο-αμερικανικής παράδοσης.

Μετά από αυτή τη σύντομη εισαγωγή, η έκθεση εισέρχεται στην ουσία του έργου, διερευνώντας καλές πρακτικές στον τομέα της οπτικής επικοινωνίας και του οπτικού γραμματισμού στην Ευρώπη. Οι εταίροι όχι μόνο μελέτησαν το ευρωπαϊκό πλαίσιο, αλλά έλαβαν επίσης υπόψη τους τις κατευθυντήριες γραμμές που παρέχονται από την Αμερικανική Επαγγελματική Ένωση Κολεγιακών και Ερευνητικών Βιβλιοθηκών για να καθορίσουν τις ικανότητες που πρέπει να αποκτήσουν οι οπτικά εγγράμματα φοιτήτριες/ εγγράμματοι φοιτητές κατά τη διάρκεια της τριτοβάθμιας εκπαίδευσής τους.

Τέλος, οι εταίροι διεξήγαγαν εις βάθος συνεντεύξεις με άτομα που μελετούν και επαγγελματίες του τομέα του οπτικού γραμματισμού. Αυτοί/ Αυτές οι εμπειρογνώμονες βοήθησαν να γίνει κατανοητή η σημασία της βελτίωσης των δεξιοτήτων οπτικού γραμματισμού τόσο στην ακαδημαϊκή εκπαίδευση όσο και στην καθημερινή ζωή.

Για να σχεδιαστεί το Μάθημα μικρομάθησης, αποφασίστηκε μια δομή που αποτελείται από μια εισαγωγή και τέσσερις διδακτικές ενότητες. Οι ενότητες αυτές καλύπτουν όλες τις βασικές πτυχές που σχετίζονται με τις εικόνες, αντλώντας πολύτιμες γνώσεις που συγκεντρώθηκαν μέσω των συνεντεύξεων και της εκτεταμένης έρευνας σχετικά με καλές πρακτικές. Αυτή η διπλή προσέγγιση εξασφάλισε τη συμπερίληψη σημαντικών θεμάτων, εξοπλίζοντας τις εκπαιδευόμενες/ τους εκπαιδευόμενους τόσο με μια βαθιά κατανόηση του ρόλου των εικόνων, όσο και με δεξιότητες ώστε να αλληλεπιδρούν κριτικά με αυτές. Συμπερασματικά, μετά την ολοκλήρωση του Μαθήματος μικρομάθησης αναμένεται ότι τα άτομα που θα συμμετέχουν θα διαθέτουν τις ικανότητες ενός εγγράμματος, στα οπτικά μέσα, ατόμου.

Sintesi

Con il dominio diffuso dei media visivi su varie piattaforme, dai social media ai notiziari e alle industrie dell'intrattenimento, il modo in cui la conoscenza viene acquisita e diffusa ha subito una trasformazione significativa.

Questo resoconto analizza il profondo impatto delle immagini sulla cultura contemporanea e il modo in cui esse ridefiniscono il concetto di istruzione. Soprattutto con l'avvento delle tecnologie digitali le immagini stanno sempre più diventando parte integrante dell'ambiente (culturale) che ci circonda, trasformando il modo in cui la conoscenza viene acquisita e condivisa. Le università svolgono un ruolo cruciale nel guidare e dare forma a questa profonda transizione culturale.

Per questo motivo, uno dei punti chiave dell'impegno di CLIP è la promozione dell'alfabetizzazione visiva nei curricula accademici, riconoscendone il ruolo fondamentale nel plasmare le abitudini di consumo di informazioni degli studenti europei nell'era digitale. Per raggiungere questo obiettivo, il progetto CLIP ha sviluppato un corso sull'alfabetizzazione visiva suddiviso in piccole unità di apprendimento.

Per comprendere adeguatamente l'importanza dell'alfabetizzazione visiva, il report inizia esplorando l'origine del termine "cultura visiva" – che risale agli anni Venti – per poi soffermarsi sull'emergere, nel corso degli anni Novanta, dei due principali campi di studi visivi: quello che fa capo alla tradizione tedesca e quello di matrice anglo-americana.

Dopo questa breve introduzione, il report entra nel vivo del progetto prendendo in considerazione alcune buone pratiche nel campo della comunicazione e dell'alfabetizzazione visiva in Europa. I partner non si sono però limitati ad analizzare i progetti europei, ma hanno esaminato anche le linee guida fornite dall'American Professional Association of College & Research Libraries per definire le competenze necessarie all'acquisizione di un'alfabetizzazione visuale nella scuola superiore.

Infine, i partner hanno intervistato studiosi e professionisti del settore visivo. Anche loro hanno sottolineato l'importanza di migliorare le competenze nel campo della alfabetizzazione visuale sia nel corso della formazione universitaria, che nella vita quotidiana.

I partner hanno deciso quindi di progettare il corso di "microformazione" suddividendolo in un modulo introduttivo e altri quattro di approfondimento. Questi moduli coprono tutti gli aspetti essenziali legati alle immagini, attingendo ai preziosi spunti emersi durante le interviste e dalla ricerca approfondita sulle "best practices". Questo doppio approccio garantisce l'inclusione degli argomenti più significativi su questo tema, così da fornire gli studenti una profonda comprensione del ruolo delle immagini e delle competenze necessarie per interagire criticamente con esse.

In conclusione, dopo aver completato il corso di "microapprendimento" ci aspettiamo quindi che gli studenti possiedano le competenze di base dell'alfabetizzazione visuale.

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The problem of the twenty-first century is the problem of the image
W. J. T. Mitchell

Rationale for this Study and Methodology

This study aims to explore the profound impact of images on contemporary culture and how they have redefined the concept of education in contemporaneity. With the widespread dominance of visual media across various platforms, ranging from social media to news outlets and entertainment industries, the way knowledge is acquired and disseminated has undergone a significant transformation.

Moreover, the study advocates for the incorporation of visual literacy into educational curricula to empower students with critical thinking, social and intercultural competencies, and effective communication skills essential for civic discourse emphasizing the importance of visual literacy education.

Universities have a crucial role in countering misinformation, reducing bias in visual representations, and promoting media and visual literacy.

By nurturing students' self-awareness and empowering them to critically analyse and interpret visual content, they can develop a deeper understanding of the politics of representation in media. Visual literacy equips students with the skills to discern biased portrayals, challenge dominant narratives, identify disinformation, and recognize the power dynamics at play in visual culture.

A key focus of CLIP's efforts lies in promoting critical visual literacy, recognizing its fundamental role in shaping the information consumption habits of European students and citizens in the digital age through a micro-learning course on critical visual literacy, designed after having conducted a deep analysis of the best practices within the field of visual communication. In this way, we gathered valuable knowledge and inspiration from a wide range of perspectives and approaches, both in Europe and in other global regions.

In addition, during the research, the project partners conducted a series of in-depth conversations with visual studies and visual communication professionals, including film directors, advertisers, video journalists, and museum experts. From theoretical and practical perspectives, these interviews offered significant insights into the importance of improving visual literacy skills in higher education and daily life.

In conclusion, by addressing this crucial aspect, the CLIP project aims to enhance the digital capabilities of the higher education sector to empower students to become more discerning and informed consumers and producers of visual content.

Introduction

On the 10th of October 2022, the European Commission launched its guidelines¹ for empowering teachers and educators to address disinformation and cultivate digital literacy through education and training. The objective is to encourage the responsible utilisation of digital technologies and the promotion of increased public awareness and knowledge regarding disinformation. The Guideline represents a crucial output of the 2021-2027 Digital Education Action Plan (DEAP), the European Commission's policy initiative that supports the effective and sustainable adaptation of high-quality, inclusive, and accessible digital education of EU member states.

There is an increasing urgency to promote not only Digital literacy, but also Media and Information Literacy (MIL) and Visual Literacy (VL) at all educational levels, both at school and among citizens. From one hand, MIL is considered by UNESCO and the EU one of the most relevant resources for promoting a critical approach to the ever-increasing mass of information we receive through media, especially in a digital field,² and to enable individuals to navigate the digital environment safely, responsibly, and critically. They acknowledge the role of MIL in strengthening democratic values, promoting media pluralism, and fostering inclusive and informed societies. This effort aims to equip individuals with the abilities to critically engage with media, understand messages, participate effectively in the contemporary information landscape, and track disinformation and bias in communication, most of which occurs online.

On the other hand, this discrepancy between the technical and critical skills required to handle media (and particularly visual media) is seen as a serious threat to democracy. In fact, nowadays, despite the younger generation's natural proficiency in creating and manipulating visual content through digital technologies, this does not necessarily translate into a critical usage of images. Promoting visual literacy at all educational levels, as well as among citizens, has become increasingly urgent to empower students (and the public) to discern disinformation and biases in visual communication. Being educated in today's context is crucial to acquire the ability to comprehend visual information correctly and navigate the visual landscape, discerning the authenticity, credibility, and biases of the images encountered.

As Hans Belting (Belting, 2010) reminds us, the political use of images is increasingly marked in times of mediocracy. Images can take deep root in the collective imagination to such an extent to influence people's behaviour. Even further, with the advent of digital technologies, images increasingly constitute the (cultural) environment that envelopes us (see for instance Pinotti, 2017 and 2021)³.

To properly understand the meaning of visual literacy, it's important to first explore the origins of the term 'visual culture'. We will then take into consideration the two distinct fields

¹<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a224c235-4843-11ed-92ed-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

²See, UNESCO, <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/media-and-information-literacy-critical-approach-literacy-digital-word>; see also Carlsson, 2019.

³Above all, see the ERC Advanced Grant project *An-Icon: History, Theory, and Practices of Environmental Images* coordinated by Andrea Pinotti, <https://an-icon.unimi.it/>.

of research, one in the United States called “Visual Cultural Studies” and the other in Europe called “Bildwissenschaft” (“Theory of image”⁴) emerged after a significant shift in the way images were perceived and consumed after the huge transformation occurred in the iconosphere.

Visual Culture: the origin of the term

While the beginning of the two fields of visual studies (German and Anglo-American) can be traced back to the mid-1990s, the origin of the concept of *visual culture* dates much farther back in the writings of a few theorists who around the mid-1920s wondered about the impact that the invention of photography and cinema had on the culture of their time, like Béla Balázs and László Moholy-Nagy, “which in their writings use the German terms ‘visuelle Kultur’, ‘optische Kultur’ e ‘Scaukulture’ to describe the epochal transformations produced by photography and cinema considered as optical media capable of redefining the coordinates of the visible and the relationship between images and words, vision, reading, visual experience and conceptual knowledge”. (Pinotti & Somaini, 2016, 3).⁵

Béla Balázs noted the advent of a new turn in the direction of the visual by a revolutionary technology that had just emerged: the cinematograph. According to the Hungarian film theorist, this new technique of seeing would give rise to a culture that is radically different from the culture produced by writing. It introduces a new universal language that has the potential to reshape societal norms and values to contrast the accelerated process of human body reification produced by the previous technology of printing (Balázs, 1924).

Similarly, in the years in which Béla Balázs wrote his essay, artist and theorist and Bauhaus instructor László Moholy-Nagy in some of his writings used the terms “optical culture” and “visual culture” to define a new mode of the visible opened by the invention of photography and cinema. Phenomena hitherto inaccessible to the human eye are made visible by the machinic eye, thus profoundly restructuring the field of the visible.

Studying visual culture, therefore, means emphasising the way people see the world, how they mediate the world through various forms of representation, how images come into being, and how they circulate, without restricting this reflection to painting, sculpture, or any other artistic or popular pictures, but focus instead on how we look at other people or a landscape. As William J. T. Mitchell remembers during an interview, when he started his first courses in this pioneering field, his interest was in the aspect of vision related to “its constructedness, its symbolic and imaginal formations” and “the anthropological concept of vision as artefactual, conventional, and artificial” (Dikovitskaya, 2001, 6).

⁴ To translate *Bildwissenschaft* as “Theory of image” is an approximation, since – as Hans Belting remind us – “... the meaning of the German word *Bild* includes image, picture, figure and illustration, the term *Bildwissenschaft* has no equivalence in the English language”. (Bredenkamp, 2003, 418).

⁵ “[...] utilizzano nei loro scritti i termini tedeschi “visuelle Kultur”, “optische Kultur” e “Scaukulture” – rispettivamente cultura visuale, cultura ottica e cultura della visione – per descrivere le trasformazioni epocali prodotti da fotografia e cinema considerati come media ottici capaci di ridefinire le coordinate del visibile e il rapporto tra immagini e parole, visione lettura, esperienza visiva e sapere concettuale”. My translation.

“Visual Cultural Studies” and “Bildwissenschaft”: the recognition of the visual as crucial aspect of human experience

Society today is highly visual, and we are constantly surrounded by images that circulate relentlessly in the iconosphere⁶ (Internet, smartphones, televisions, newspapers, and magazines) and the new “pictorial turn” coined by W. J. T. Mitchell⁷ – or his counterpart in German based culture of “iconic turn” used in the very same years by Gottfried Bohem⁸ – implies that images have become central to communication and meaning-making. The image is by no means a new theme but rather a different mode of thinking, capable of highlighting and exploiting the specific cognitive possibilities of non-verbal representations – as Bohem wrote in a famous letter to Mitchell in which he reasoned about the relationship between Anglo-American visual cultural studies (or more briefly visual culture) and the German *Bildwissenschaft* (“science” or “theory of image”)⁹ and the legitimacy of their scientific work.

For his part, Mitchell asserts that the pictorial turn signifies a move away from an exclusively text-based culture toward one that values and engages with visual representations. Even though this turn, as Mitchell recalls, is a trope that reappears at any moment in the history of culture when some new technology appears on the scene. That is why every pictorial turn involves a “specific picture that emerges in a particular historical situation” (Mitchell, 2008, 15). Mitchell, in his books explores the transformative power of images and argues for the recognition of their central position in contemporary society. “The widely shared notion that visual images have replaced words as the dominant mode of expression in our time” (Mitchell, 2005, 5). It denotes a fundamental reorientation of our perception, cognition, and communication processes, emphasising the significance of images as powerful vehicles of meaning and knowledge. The purpose of Mitchell is “namely, explaining what pictures are, how they mean, what they do, while reviving an ancient interdisciplinary enterprise called iconology (the general study of images across the media) and opening a new initiative called visual culture the study of human visual experience and expression)” (Mitchell, 2005, 6) – as he stated in *What Do Pictures Want?* A collection of his essays on image theory written between 1994 and 2002.

What does Visual Literacy mean? An introduction on the concept

The impact of images on contemporary culture has redefined the notion of being educated in today's society – as we state before. Images have become pervasive, dominating social media platforms, advertisements, news outlets, and entertainment industries. Consequently,

⁶ For the definition and the history of the concept see, M. Di Monte, *Iconosphere*, “International Lexicon of Aesthetics”, Spring 2018 edition, <https://lexicon.mimesisjournals.com/archive/2018/spring/Iconosphere.pdf>.

⁷ First appeared in *Artforum* 1992: 89–94 and then reprinted in *Picture Theory* (W.J.T. Mitchell 1994: 11–35).

⁸ G. Boheme writes of “Ikonische Wende” in his essay *Il ritorno delle immagini*, in A. Pinotti & S. Somaini (eds.) *Teoria dell'immagine*, 39-72 “concepito come ampio progetto di ricerca sulla logica specifica delle immagini e sul ruolo costitutivo in diversi campi del sapere” (26). My translation.

⁹ Both fields of research emerged around the 1900s, united by a common interest in the cultural significance of images and vision. Besides these similarities, the two approaches have since developed according to different assumptions and goals. (See for more details, for example, A. Pinotti & A. Somaini, *Cultura visuale*, Einaudi, Torino 2016, 17-37).

the rise of visual media, particularly in the digital age, has fundamentally altered the landscape of education and reshaped the understanding of knowledge acquisition. They possess the capacity to convey complex ideas, emotions, and information in a concise and visually appealing manner, so much so that the ability to interpret and critically engage with images has become an essential skill in contemporary culture, redefining what it means to be educated. But images can also influence public opinion, reinforce stereotypes, challenge social norms, and spark cultural and political movements.

They play a pivotal role in structuring our collective memory, cultural identity, and social interactions. “In visual language, meaning is apparent on a basic level, but visual language is a complex code that must be learned for true comprehension. We have to learn how to read visuals” (Avgerinou & Pettersson, 2011, 8).

What should be defined as Visual Literacy?

We are aware in fact that saying “read images” is a contradiction in itself, and visual literacy does not avoid it, but on the contrary, underlines it. “Tropes of reading are unavoidable in talk about images”– as Elkins reminds us, quoting a Mitchell’s essay devoted to exploring the metaphor embedded here: “Seeing is something like reading” (Mitchell, 2008, 11). And, it is not the case, since reading is much more difficult to acquire than seeing, which seems an “easily and naturally acquired skill” to learn (Mitchell, 2008, 13), at least at its basic level.

Under another perspective, Suzanne Stokes, associate professor at Troy State University, in her contribution to visual literacy in teaching and learning, gives us an overview on the educational literature. The article offers review of research studies that explore the impact on the instructional approaches incorporating visual components at various levels, providing a clear definition of Visual Literacy, from the educational perspective, quoting Wileman: “The ability to read, interpret, and understand information presented in pictorial or graphic images” (Stokes, 2002, 12). This article helps to reflect on the integrating visual enhancements in teaching and promoting the cultivation of students’ visual skills in combination with the development of more traditional abilities, from verbal to reading to mathematics. “The use of visual literacy ideas and strategies to enhance verbal learning is important (Flattley, 1998; Sinatra, 1986). Because visual literacy precedes verbal literacy in human development, it is the basic literacy in the thought processes that are the foundations for reading and writing” (Stokes, 2002, 13).

Additionally, Suzanne Stokes references The European Research Infrastructure Consortium's (ERIC)¹⁰ definition of visual literacy as “a group of competencies that allows humans to discriminate and interpret the visible action, objects, and/or symbols, natural or constructed, that they encounter in the environment”. Another perspective comes from Robinson (as quoted in Sinatra, 1986), who views visual literacy as “an organising force in promoting understanding, retention, and recall of so many academic concepts with which students must contend”. Lastly, Sinatra defines visual literacy as “the active reconstruction of past visual experience with incoming visual messages to obtain meaning” emphasising the learner's active role in creating recognition.

Furthermore, the advent of digital technology and the ease of image creation and dissemination have democratised visual expression. Anyone with a smartphone and an internet connection can create and share images, contributing to a vast visual ecosystem. As a result, being educated involves not only consuming images but also actively participating in image creation, curation, and analysis. It requires individuals to become proficient in visual communication, harnessing the power of images to convey ideas, advocate for causes, and engage in meaningful dialogues.

Therefore, the definition of visual literacy is more comprehensive than Wilemans’ definition, as it includes the *production* of images and not just the capacity to critically understand visual language and recognize the intended messages and underlying narratives of images.

¹⁰The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

In summary, visual literacy in the digital era should include tools to interpret and decipher visual and media content, and additional tools to produce and disseminate personally created visual materials accompanied by information and attribution rights. “A visually literate individual is both a critical consumer of visual media and a competent contributor to a body of shared knowledge and culture”. (ACRL, 2011)

In-depth analysis of good practices in the field in Europe and beyond

In this section, we will explore a few exemplary practices within the field of visual communications and visual literacy, both in Europe and other global regions. By analysing these remarkable initiatives, we aim to gain valuable insights and inspiration from diverse perspectives and approaches. These case studies serve as indication to the innovative and impactful work being done in visual studies, contributing to the advancement of knowledge, and understanding in this field.

Each partner collected almost 30 cases, following different criteria, to cover a broader area of Media Literacy in Europe, and overseas.

ALL DIGITAL researched the archives of projects – involved as partners – sharing results from their past experiences in both projects and policies in the field.

IULM University and Hellenic Open University (HOU) paid attention, on the one hand, to academic cases both in Italy and in Greece, which are most related to the topics addressed in the project, using the following keywords: visual media literacy, courses, programs, and activities. On the other hand, IULM focused on the guidelines listed by the Association of College & Research Libraries (ACRL) – a division of the American Library Association (ALA) – created for listing the competencies students should obtain in the visual communication area. HOU selected a few examples of activities and resources found on the web which are relative to the topics of the project.

UNIMED collected cases from different sources: partially paying attention to those universities particularly keen on developing visual literacy skills in the scholarship; and partially considering those collaborative platforms, such as *Ersilia*, which offers an accessible way for people to acquire media and literacy education.

After the desk research, a consultation among partners was conducted in order to analyse the findings in depth and select the most appropriate for drafting the Clip WP2 Report.

Here we present the five best practices selected among those cases solely dedicated to teaching Visual communication, leaving out those dedicated to Media and Digital literacy.

According to the objectives of the Commission's Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027, which aims to make education even more responsive to helping learners “to develop the ability to critically approach, filter and assess information, notably to identify disinformation and to manage the overload of information”, the expected impacts of WP1 Report was to identify best practices, and to analyse them, for better understanding:

- (1) critical aspects of the role of images in contemporary communication;
- (2) how to help people to teach and to learn, through an inclusive debate, “reading”, and dealing with images;
- (3) how to contrast online visual disinformation, developing a critical thinking and scientific approach to images;
- (4) how to work with images, using different perspectives: from a historical point of view to theoretical and practical ones;

(5) how to apply visual literacy skills in scholarship research, coursework, and professional practices.

This analysis can inform the design and the implementation of the online CLIP course, in visual literacy, which will be produced by the project. Each case highlights certain aspects that correspond to the skills required to develop critical competencies, essential for dealing with images and visual media in the contemporary digital environment.

The Five Good Practices

What's Going on in This Picture? The learning Network by *The New York Times*

Since 1998, the website *Learning Network* has provided each school year free teaching lessons and activities based on *The New York Times* content - articles, essays, images, videos, graphics, and podcasts - to help people to teach and learn in several subject areas. Among the six possible features presented on their site, the one that interests us is the *Photos, Graphs & Videos* section, in which they introduce the weekly activity called [What's Going on in This Picture?](#)¹¹.

Every Sunday night, *The New York Times* uploads a photograph chosen from the newspaper's archive without its caption: they ask students to think about it critically and figure out what is represented by the picture. On Mondays, they open a discussion with the help of [Visual Thinking Strategies](#) partner – an education non-profit which uses a specific teaching approach to create inclusive debate, initially focused on artistic images (and later implemented to include all images). This method has demonstrated to have a positive knock-on effect on the audience. Students are invited to imagine the stories behind the pictures, submit their own captions and share their opinion during conversations moderated by experts until Thursday afternoon. On that day, the NYT team reveals the true history behind the photograph.

ERSILIA: Tool for Visual Literacy

Launched in 2017, *Ersilia*¹² is the result of a collaboration between the Evens Foundation and the educational team of *LEBAL* – the acclaimed research and exhibition space in Paris dedicated to visual studies. *Ersilia* is a collaborative digital platform and a pedagogical tool that introduces an original and critical way of learning, teaching, and sharing knowledge about how to “read” and deal with images. It has been implemented over the years by its actual users: artists, teachers, and students. Considering images as “political territories” rather than neutral objects, *Ersilia* fosters a critical understanding of the conditions in which images are produced, circulated, and assimilated. The platform provides various tools such as a selection of images, games, critical essays, and methodologies that can be used in the teaching context. The highlights of this project – summarised in the site presentation – is to actively involve all the participants, so that each class can develop its own activities based on the analyses conducted with the support of team experts whose expertise covers several fields (such as semiology, aesthetics, history, politics, sociology, and media studies). All these different points of view promote a critical understanding of the conditions in which images are produced, circulated, and assimilated, since images cannot be considered neutral objects, but on the opposite, they are cultural representational products imbued with political ideas and bias that should be revealed and interpreted.

¹¹ <https://www.nytimes.com/column/learning-whats-going-on-in-this-picture> [Accessed 3 May 2023].

¹² <https://evensfoundation.be/projects/ersilia-i-tool-for-visual-literacy> [Accessed 28 January 2023].

YOUVERIFY! Savoir Devenir

Following the success of *Youcheck*, – a pilot project website aimed at countering visual misinformation among young people through a pedagogical program by using Agence France-Presse [https://www.afp.com/en] *InVID-WeVerify* plugin – a professional fact-checking tool – *Youverify*'s¹³ the overall goal is to expand that project and massively disseminate it to extend the number of beneficiaries. The purpose of the website is to train an increasingly broad audience of educational mediators (such as librarians and teachers), undergraduate and graduate students, and the general public, to develop a critical thinking and scientific approach to images for contrasting online visual disinformation. They provide a selection of resources among which it is worth mentioning two interesting tools: *Le MOOC “La désinformation pas à pas”* a free and open-to-everyone online course, and *YouCheck! détectives*, a so-called “serious game” against disinformation.

Le MOOC is articulated in six modules, whose purpose is to acquire critical thinking in both the Media and Information field. Particular attention is paid to developing those skills needed to familiarise oneself with images in the digital context. Furthermore, the course aims to implement the tools required to verify the information we access through photographs and videos circulating on the Internet, probably the largest image and media distribution and the most extensive propaganda machine ever invented in human history.

YouCheck! Detectives, a game against false news designed for teenagers and up, uses the visual verification plug-in *InVID-WeVerify* to explain the fundamentals for recognising fabricated or inaccurate video and image information through six tasks, learning by doing.

MIL, Media and Information Literacy, University of Gothenburg

Media and Information Literacy (MIL) is central for the University of Gothenburg (UGOT)¹⁴, which in April 2019 established the *GPS 400* centre for collaborative research on visual media. The centre, which comprises representatives of four different faculties of UGOT, undertakes collaborative visual research together with archives, libraries, museums, NGOs, commercial partners, and civic society. Those interdisciplinary experts test, develop and investigate visual source material to disseminate empirically valid knowledge about past, present and future uses, and representations of images with the help of innovative models and methods.

Under the MIL label, *GPS 400* has launched an interdisciplinary research team: the *VIMIK-group*, with audio-visual and pedagogy experts. The group aims to enhance regional competence and to function as an accessible arena in the local environment for improving the ability to understand and interpret images, but also to work with them, using different perspectives: from a historical point of view to theoretical and practical ones. They regularly ensure as they state on their website: “That collaborative knowledge development and democratic knowledge exchanges are regularly carried out and made available via digital

¹³ <https://savoirdevenir.net/you-verify/> [Accessed 22 January 2023].

¹⁴ <https://www.gu.se/en/collaborative-visual-research/node/90634/visual-media-and-information-literacy> [Accessed 13 January 2023].

technology and in the public space”. They also provide school and research activities through workshops and webinars offered to students as part of their school education, as well as training activities for teachers or staff working in archives, museums, libraries, and companies.

VISUAL & MEDIA LITERACY GUIDE, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth

This *Visual and Media Literacy LibGuide*¹⁵ provides faculties, and students with the tools to develop and to apply visual literacy skills in scholarship research, coursework, and professional practices. The guide includes the seven standards - presented later in this report - designed by the American Association of College and Research Libraries, a division of the American Library Association (ALA/ACRL), best practices, and fair use principles along with resources for instruction, creation, documentation, and deliberation of visual and media literacy.

One of the exercises proposed, for instance, is a result of a collaboration with the Toledo Museum of Art, since as they state, “Art museums [are] the repositories of the greatest examples of visual communication in human history, are specially equipped to help people learn how to unlock the meanings of images”. This method, called *The Art of Seeing Art*TM, is structured into six steps an observer should follow when s/he looks at any work of art presented in the collection, and it is extensively valid for all images encountered in everyday life. When observers are in front of an image, the general suggestion is to slow down and take time to look at it attentively, since every picture presents so many details that it is impossible to catch all of them at first glance. After looking, observing, and seeing (in this order) an image, the fourth move is to describe it precisely. This process would help the observers in organising their thoughts and build an inventory of objects, figures, and settings. Finally, the observer should analyse and give her/his interpretation using her/his previous own knowledge together with any information s/he should find about the creator, the context in which that image has been produced, and so on.

¹⁵ <https://guides.lib.umassd.edu/visualliteracyguide> [Accessed 7 January 2023].

Guidelines by the American professional associations ALA/ACRL

In addition to these projects for teaching visual literacy – which are considered some of the most innovative and engaging proposals in both Europe and the United States – it is very interesting to take a deeper look at the guidelines outlined by the American professional Association of College & Research Libraries, a division of the American Library Association (ALA/ACRL)¹⁶. They created them to precisely define the competencies a visually literate student should acquire during their higher education. They serve as a road map for us to ensure that these skills are effectively covered and accomplished through the modules of our online micro-learning course.

1: The visually literate student determines the nature and extent of the visual materials needed.

This first step is divided into two moments: firstly, the student defines which role should have an image used within a project and conveys criteria that should be met by the image. The learning outcome for this step is to delineate the purpose and the environment where to use the planned image, articulates criteria and finds appropriate terms to describe the chosen images.

Secondly, the visually literate student recognises a variety of image sources. As a learning result the student should explore, identify, and analyse a range of image sources and formats. S/he is aware that same images can be modified or reused in different contexts with different meanings.

2: The visually literate student finds, and accesses needed images and visual media effectively and efficiently.

For this step the student should reach three levels of results. First, s/he identifies interdisciplinary and discipline-specific image sources; s/he articulates the advantages and disadvantages of various types of image sources and retrieval systems; and s/he recognises how the image search process is affected by image rights and use restrictions.

As a second moment, the student conducts effective image research developing an appropriate strategy; recognising the role of textual information in providing access to image content using keywords. S/he will be also aware of other possible organisations (e.g., absence of full-text search, variations in controlled vocabularies, lack of subject terms) and how it can affect the research.

Finally, the visually literate student acquires and organises images and source information reproducing the needed image using appropriate technology.

3: The visually literate student interprets and analyses the meanings of images and visual media.

The visually literate student identifies information relevant to an image's meaning, observing content and physical details. S/he also reads text that accompanies an image to learn about

¹⁶https://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org.acrl/files/content/standards/Framework_Companion_Visual_Literacy.pdf [Accessed 5 April 2023].

it. S/he identifies the subject of an image; s/he examines the relationship among different images; s/he questions herself about possible additional research images needed.

Moreover s/he should be capable of situating an image in its cultural, social, and historical contexts, which means describing relevant cultural and historical factors to be able to interpret the image in its original context and to identify bias (gender, ethnicity, and other cultural or social identifiers).

The student identifies the physical, technical, and design components of an image, noticing specific elements of an image (composition, contrast, repetition, style, and such) together with techniques, technologies, or materials used to produce an image.

As a last step of this standard, the student validates interpretation and analysis of images through discourse with other students, scholars, and experts.

4: The visually literate student evaluates images and their sources.

The student evaluates how effectively an image achieves a specific purpose and determines the reliability of graphical representations of data.

The visually literate student appraises the aesthetic and technical characteristics and the quality of images.

The trainee analyses textual information that goes along with images for accuracy, reliability and completeness and verifies that information by consulting multiple sources.

The student makes judgments about the reliability and accuracy of image sources based on evaluations of authority, point of view and bias.

5: The visually literate student uses images and visual media effectively.

The visually literate student uses images productively for strategic usage for interdisciplinary research, communication, and learning projects for different goals such as: illustrations, evidence, visual models, primary sources, and focus of analysis.

The student uses appropriate editing, presentation, communication, storage, media tools and applications to prepare and work with images.

The student employs problem solving, creativity, and experimentation to incorporate images into academic projects.

The student communicates competently with and about images considering meaning, aesthetic criteria, visual impact, rhetorical impact, and audience. S/he integrates images with textual information critically considering her/his strategy of using images to communicate.

6: The visually literate student designs and creates meaningful images and visual media.

The student produces visual materials using aesthetic and design choices, for a specific target, to communicate concepts, narratives, arguments, and evaluate her products.

7: The visually literate student understands many of the ethical, legal, social, and economic issues surrounding the creation and use of images and visual media, and accesses and uses visual materials ethically.

The student understands many of the ethical, social, and economic issues together with intellectual property rights that surround images and visual media. S/he recognises policies on access to image and disseminates personal created images with attribution information and intellectual properties rights.

In conclusion, for designing our online course, we considered the five best practices that guided our selection of activities to propose to the students and informed our approach to involve them in the platform and encourage their active participation. Additionally, we drew inspiration from the abilities outlined by ALA/ACRL in their guidelines for visual literacy competency to structure the course into distinct modules based on the analysed criteria.

Visual talks with experts: an analysis of the results of the interviews

For collecting opinions and suggestions on the above-mentioned issues, we carried out in-depth conversations with scholars – in visual studies and visual communication– and practitioners in the visual field: film and video directors; film and tv critics; advertising professionals, and video journalists – which helped us to understand the importance of improving visual literacy skills in both higher education and in everyday life, from different perspectives, theoretical and practical. As Boehm underlined: “Those who are fascinated by images in the most fundamental way, those who have thoroughly examined and analysed great numbers of them and possess what one could call an image-sense, know with *certainty* that there is such a thing as an *iconic intelligence* that the artist restores in order to free himself from the demands of language, from canonical texts, or from other mimetic instances, and to establish *evidences* of a *unique type*, also – and especially – in cases involving e.g. traditional historical images that re-tell the time-worn content of the bible, mythology, or history” providing us with a solid framework to guide our selection regarding whom to interview (Boehm & Mitchell, 2009, 106).

On the one hand, academic researchers highlighted the crucial role of images from a theoretical perspective, emphasising how visual representations shape our understanding of reality, challenge assumptions, and prompt profound philosophical investigations. On the other hand, filmmakers and video journalists offer us critical and practical insights into the proper use of pictures in daily professional activity, addressing ethical and critical concerns. Furthermore, experts from art museums and galleries, who possess deep insights and expertise in the visual field, explain us the complex and stratified nature of pictures, from paintings and drawings to all possible different other pictures, such as photographs, charts, drawings, graphs, videos, movies, or other image visualisation.

To give a more concrete idea of the breadth of the themes that emerged during our conversations with experts, we can quote a few passages from some of the interviews as an account of the varied and multifaceted backgrounds from which the reflections on the visual arose. A snapshot – to stay on topic – of how images interrogate today the most diversified contexts of contemporaneity.

Honorary Professor of the Department of Philosophy at Sapienza, University of Rome, **Pietro Montani** illuminated the fundamental issue of the image – its technical reproducibility in the twentieth century and today its digital manipulability as last and very significant episode – to show, on a practical level, the human imagination at work, inseparable from the technologies with which it has been entangled since its origin. Without going into the dense examination conducted in the interview after his last publication *Destini tecnologici dell'immaginazione* (2022), we just recall here Pietro Montani's opinion on the urgency of teaching visual culture in schools of all levels¹⁷. It is the educational system that must oversee teaching the critical aspects of contemporary technological devices, the use of which is extremely widespread especially in the young (and very young) generations, but without critical training on them. To date, learning how to use these devices (above all the

¹⁷Interview with Pietro Montani, 7 April 2023.

smartphones) has been self-directed and basically left in the hands of market influence. If our goal is to increase awareness of the use of digital technologies in the production of syncretic forms, it is essential to consider visual education as a pivotal and crucial subject of every school curriculum.

Regarding the interviews with directors, filmmakers, and video journalists, in a word with those who work with images, we report here below an excerpt from the conversation with **Martina Parenti**. The director, with her partner Massimo D'Anolfi, wrote, filmed, edited, and produced film length movies selected in many international film festivals. Just to mention a few: *I promessi sposi (The Betrothed, 2006)*, selected at the Locarno Film Festival in 'Ici & Ailleurs', the film was awarded at the Festival dei Popoli and at the Filmmaker Film Festival in Milan. *Il Castello (The Castle, 2011)* was awarded at Hot Docs, Toronto with the Special Jury Prize and in EIDF, Seoul with the Special Jury Award, at IDA Awards in Los Angeles with the Prize for the Best Cinematography, at Torino Film Festival with the Premio Speciale della Giuria Italiana.doc and Premio Avanti. In 2016 *Spira Mirabilis* premiered in competition during Mostra Internazionale d'arte cinematografica di Venezia 73. They are now working on the film *Bestiari, Erbari, Lapidari (2004)*.

During our conversation, we considered their significant film production marked by research work in historical archives. Such research has allowed them to redefine, in a new context, images produced for non-aesthetic purposes, such as war or medical-scientific footage. Through editing and recontextualization, Martina Parenti and Massimo D'Anolfi gave a new frame of meaning to the archival images. "Archives are living places", Martina Parenti points out, "animated by people who have consciously chosen to catalogue footage. They are fundamental places since they preserve an iconic memory that can (and must) be constantly interrogated to bring out new meanings and make different sense depending on who is watching them, the historical context in which they are transposed, and the objectives of the research"¹⁸.

To mention another interview, we would like to quote **Janos Keresnyei**, who has been a journalist for 30 years and has run local television and different television and radio channels as a manager and editor-in-chief. In parallel, he also teaches at the university as a lecturer in Media Literacy. We asked him his opinion on the most valuable skills to achieve in higher education to become a visually literate student. He declares that especially today, in such a sophisticated visual communication environment "students should develop their skills to understand the importance of the context and the text, the image, the sources of information, and even the visual context where the image appears, then the student could recognize "Is that true or not?"¹⁹.

From the side of the history of art, we would like to report the words of the artist and Educator and Creative Programmes Developer at Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna, **Lara Verena Bellenghi**, which pointed out the always constructed and multifaceted nature of every image, embedded with symbols and cultural meanings. To fully understand a picture, though, we cannot use only the dense yet ambiguous information present into it. Instead, it is essential to seek clarification from additional informational sources that provide contextual

¹⁸ Interview with Martina Parenti, 24 April 2023.

¹⁹ Interview with Janos Keresnyei, 17 May 2023.

insights for understanding the intended meanings of a picture, and the various influences embedded, such as the values, background, and bias of the creator²⁰. Additionally, **Paolo De Gasperis** - Explora Children's Museum's Head of the digital sector and scientific director, and PhD in contemporary art at Sapienza University of Rome - gave us some insights on the impact gamification and visual literacy have on people and children's learning process. Quoting his interview: "In a Children's Museum, the game is the driver, it is the vector with which the educational contents are passed, and it is the primary mediator of contents. Therefore, places like a Children's Museum, or in general places where non-formal teaching, informal teaching are applied, can be places of excellence for teaching media literacy"²¹. He then proceeded to illustrate two different methods to involve young audiences in playing with Visual Media: stop motion storytelling and the usage of an open-source framework to edit interactive digital content, HP5.

To complete this overview of the collected interviews, we should quote **Gianni Canova**, the Rector of IULM University, an Italian university specialised in communication, with an emphasis on digital culture, visual studies, and the economic and social implications of contemporary media platforms. He mentioned the importance of teaching the language of film at all school levels because: "Cinema is a language that has its own history, its own grammar, its own syntax, its own chemistry, its own emotions, and that it deserves a much more organic, much more in-depth systemic approach". He then concluded with an important note on how one should generally passionately teach students: "If we think that knowledge, that training is not the transfer of knowledge already given from the professor's mind to the mind of the students, if we think that this is not what it is - and I think it is not - then the path of training must be adventurous in the etymological sense. It has to be an adventure, going towards it, and it has to start from a sense of lack. I can only teach what I don't know well and what I want to know because if I trigger the desire, this desire becomes contagious and involves everyone else as well, in a path where you know where you start, but you don't know where"²².

Moreover, IULM University features a doctoral program in Visual and Media Studies represents a didactic initiative that continually engages the most influential domestic and international scholars to equip the emerging generation of researchers with the necessary skills and knowledge in media, visual languages, and literature. **Vincenzo Trione**²³, Dean of the Faculty of Arts and Tourism, and coordinator of this program told us that the Ph. D. program "has been working over the years on the need to be in tune with a hybrid, transversal, contaminated discipline, which does not yet have a specific statute in our country, and which has nonetheless been under constant discussion for a long time. Our offer stems precisely from the need to work on this specificity of Visual Studies, understanding them as a campus, a sort of large magnetic field, within which they collide, meet, brush against, and lap each other".

Overall, to conclude our analysis of these insights and summarise them, we would like to emphasise the importance of cultivating visual literacy competencies in all disciplines and

²⁰ Interview with Lara Verena Bellenghi, 31 March 2023.

²¹ Interview with Paolo De Gasperis, 2023.

²² Interview with Gianni Canova, 5 June 2023.

²³ Interview with Vincenzo Trione, 12 June 2023.

professions, showing the enormous impact of images in our daily lives. Along with the awareness, stressed by many, both theorists and practitioners, that every image is a complex construct. Moreover, we should consider, along with visual representations, the process of vision itself as a complex, culturally constructed, and symbolical act that should be questioned and analysed. Vision is not simply a mechanical operation, rather it is a complex cognitive process that necessitates learning.

Visual Tools Box

Recommendations on the structure, content, and tools for designing the micro-learning course

For designing our micro-learning course on critical visual literacy, we decided to divide it into four modules, plus an introduction, which covers all the essential aspects linked to images based on precious insights gathered from interviews with experts in the visual domain, and on the extensive research conducted by all partners on best practices in the field – as mentioned above. This double approach provided us with a solid basis for including the most significant subjects to teach, enabling us to equip students with a deep comprehension of the role of visuals and the ability to approach images critically. To ensure an engaging learning experience, we recommend using concise video lectures (cut from the interviews collected) that capture key concepts, together with interactive activities provided on the platform and academic papers to download to deepen the specific topics covered in each module.

The introductory module serves as a warmup time for students to become familiar with the course platform, meanwhile allowing them to get acquainted with the pedagogy and assessment methods applied. The module provides students with a concise introduction to the importance of developing visual literacy skills to acquaint them with the central theme of the microlearning course.

To move on to the description of the subsequent modules: the first one – aimed at developing a *Critical looking* – will start by considering images as products of human intervention and interpretation and not as direct representations of reality. Many hidden aspects may not be immediately apparent at a glance. Additionally, we broaden the power of the invention of photography and cinema on visual culture, which has blurred the boundaries between reality and representation. We explore the impact of this influence on shaping our perceptions, beliefs, and how we interpret visual information.

The second module, *Rethink Your Eye*, will focus on the importance of being aware that all pictures carry embedded messages about the values, beliefs, and perspectives of creators. Visual media convey messages about creators, and, at the same time, reflect the cultural, ethical, and aesthetic backgrounds of viewers, shaping their interpretations and responses when engaging with images. By exploring these dimensions, learners will gain a critical understanding of how pictures influence our perceptions and values.

The third module, titled *Decoding Visual Meaning*, investigates how the significance of pictures can undergo substantial transformations, based on the contextual framework in which they are viewed. The meaning attributed to each picture depends on the accompanying texts, and on all the discourses surrounding it. Students will examine how aspects like historical, social, and cultural contexts impact the interpretation and reception of visual images.

The final module, *Preserving the Past*, explores the role of pictures – including audio-visuals, drawings, photographs, and films – as visual witnesses of the past, serving as invaluable archives for future generations. We emphasise the importance of collecting them within visual archives, which operate as vital institutions for preserving visual knowledge. Learners

will reflect on the profound significance of pictures as historical documents, exploring effective strategies for image searching, including relevant keywords and text-based queries to navigate digital archives.

By following these different modules, we will guarantee the achievement of competencies to detect image distortions and stereotypes in visual artefacts, providing learners with fundamentals of visual culture and the ability to interpret images and the accompanying texts. Students will be equipped with an advanced understanding of how many cultural prejudices and stereotypes inform images that, at first glance, appear objective and neutral. Following the microlearning course, students will also discover the latest best practices in visual communication.

After finishing the micro-learning course, we expect that students will possess the capabilities of a visually literate individual. These include the ability to identify the nature and extent of the visual materials required and to interpret and critically analyse images and visual media. Additionally, students will efficiently locate and access pictures, evaluating the reliability of archival sources and recognizing how to use pictures ethically and competently.

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